

UNITED
NATIONS

Food and Agriculture
Organization of the
United Nations

Intergovernmental Science-Policy
Platform on Biodiversity and
Ecosystem Services

The IPBES Code of Practice on the Use of Artificial Intelligence Tailored to the Needs of Assessments

Version: 1.0
February 2026

Set out as appendix II to the annex of IPBES/12/INF/12 and was welcomed by the IPBES Plenary at its 12th session, held in Manchester, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, from 3 to 8 February 2026.

Suggested citation:

IPBES (2026): IPBES Code of Practice on the Use of Artificial Intelligence, version 1.0. Krug, R. M. and Niamir, A. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17628864

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To get the latest version of the document visit <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17628864>
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Introduction

This code of practice outlines principles for the ethical and responsible use of artificial intelligence (AI) in the preparation of IPBES deliverables, in particular assessments. It provides guidance for the use of AI tools in typical assessment activities, including the collection, analysis, processing, synthesis and presentation of data and knowledge in all formats, such as written content, figures and visualisations. The use of AI in the publication and dissemination of IPBES products is beyond the scope of this code. The code is organised around representative use cases that reflect common and emerging applications of AI in IPBES knowledge synthesis. These examples are not exhaustive but illustrate relevant risks, limitations and responsibilities associated with AI use.

AI technologies involving large language models and related systems are evolving rapidly. While they offer powerful capabilities to support experts, they also introduce specific challenges, including bias in training data and algorithms, uncertainty about copyright in training material and generated content, inconsistencies in AI-generated outputs and the risk of presenting inaccurate or misleading information as fact.

In line with the platform's data and knowledge management policy, including transparency, inclusivity, openness, recognition and respect for diverse knowledge systems, and the promotion of collective benefit, AI must be used in a manner that strengthens the credibility, legitimacy, integrity and inclusivity of IPBES products. Ethical and responsible use of AI, as defined in the UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence (2021) and the UN Principles for the Ethical Use of Artificial Intelligence in the United Nations System (2022), requires transparency, accountability and fairness in all applications. Any use of AI tools in assessment preparation must therefore be documented in the corresponding data and knowledge management report to ensure traceability and accountability. Above all, responsible use of AI must maintain and foster trust among all stakeholders.

The development of this Code of Practice draws on relevant international and regional frameworks, including Governing AI for Humanity – Final Report of the United Nations High-Level Advisory Body on Artificial Intelligence¹, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) report on Biodiversity and AI: Opportunities and Recommendations for Action², and the European Union Artificial Intelligence Act³. The AI code of practice is aligned with the UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence⁴, the Principles for the Ethical Use of Artificial Intelligence in the United Nations System⁵, and relevant IPBES policies and procedures.

General principles

The following general principles apply to all uses of artificial intelligence (AI) in the preparation of IPBES assessments. They are intended to ensure that AI is used ethically, transparently and in a way that supports the credibility, legitimacy, integrity and inclusivity of IPBES products.

Responsibility and accountability. All outputs derived from or influenced by AI must be critically reviewed and evaluated by IPBES experts. Responsibility for all content, including text, graphs, scripts, citations and references, lies with the authors. AI may not be cited as a source of authority. Authors should be prepared to justify and defend the validity and appropriateness of AI-informed content in the same way as for any other assessment content.

¹ https://www.un.org/sites/un2.un.org/files/governing_ai_for_humanity_final_report_en.pdf

² <https://wp.oecd.ai/app/uploads/2025/05/biodiversity-and-AI-opportunities-recommendations-for-action.pdf>

³ <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj>

⁴ <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/recommendation-ethics-artificial-intelligence>

⁵ <https://unsceb.org/principles-ethical-use-artificial-intelligence-united-nations-system>

Transparency and disclosure. Any use of AI must be disclosed and documented in the respective data and knowledge management report (DMR). Documentation should include the purpose of use, the tool(s) used, verbatim prompts or representative excerpts, the model type and configuration, and any relevant limitations or uncertainties. Where available, experts may refer to model cards, system cards or equivalent documentation describing model characteristics. Experts should also note whether they have trained or fine-tuned a model.

Prompt design and documentation. The formulation of prompts—including their structure, wording and level of detail—strongly influences AI-generated outputs. Experts should design prompts carefully to avoid introducing bias, inaccuracies or unverified assumptions. Prompts used at any stage of the assessment should be recorded in the DMR, together with a brief description of their purpose and outcome. When online tools are used, prompts must not include confidential IPBES text or identifiers.

Bias awareness and mitigation. Experts must remain vigilant to potential biases embedded in AI models through their design, training data or post-processing. AI-generated content must be critically reviewed to avoid reinforcing stereotypes, excluding certain perspectives or introducing misleading interpretations. When biases are identified, they should be corrected using alternative approaches or acknowledged and justified in the relevant text and in the DMR.

Scientific integrity and reproducibility. Because AI systems are stochastic and opaque, reproducibility may be limited. To maintain scientific integrity, experts should follow the above guidance on traceability, transparency and accountability, and ensure that AI-supported outputs are independently verifiable to the extent possible.

Respect for data governance and intellectual property. AI must not be used in ways that infringe or circumvent copyright, licensing or data-sharing agreements. As AI models may generate or reproduce copyrighted material, outputs should be checked using non-AI methods to ensure proper attribution and to avoid plagiarism, in accordance with applicable citation standards and the IPBES code of conduct for authors.

Alignment with United Nations core values. The use of AI should respect the United Nations values of integrity, professionalism and respect for diversity. Integrity requires the application of high standards of honesty and accountability; professionalism requires that AI is used responsibly and in line with the IPBES mandate; and respect for diversity requires inclusivity and fairness, avoiding discrimination or bias in AI-assisted processes.

Guided by the IPBES data and knowledge management policy. The use of AI in IPBES assessments should adhere to the principles set out in the IPBES data and knowledge management policy.

Confidentiality. The use of AI must comply with the IPBES code of practice for experts. Assessment drafts and related materials must remain confidential. Confidential information—including assessment text, lists of candidates, experts' personal data, external review comments and internal discussions—should only be processed using private, locally hosted or institutionally provided AI tools, and not shared with public or third-party commercial systems. When online tools are used, experts should not upload entire documents and must ensure that no confidential IPBES content or identifiers are included in prompts.

Specific use cases

This section provides practical guidance for the use of AI in the production of IPBES assessments. It aims to help experts minimise risks and ensure that all AI-related activities remain consistent with the IPBES data and knowledge management policy and the general principles outlined above. Each use case illustrates both opportunities and risks associated with AI applications. These examples are not exhaustive but are intended to support responsible decision making when integrating AI into the assessment workflow. Core assessment activities, including drafting assessment text, conclusions or findings, must not be carried out by AI systems.

Editorial usage

AI is increasingly embedded in writing and editing tools. These systems assist with improving spelling, grammar and clarity and may help align text with institutional styles such as the United Nations Editorial Manual. Their use is common and often unavoidable in collaborative writing environments. AI-generated text must not be used directly in assessment drafts. Experts must independently write and verify all assessment content to ensure accuracy, neutrality and defensibility.

Spell checkers:

Usage: Continuous use during drafting and editing.

Risks: Minimal, though online tools may collect contextual data.

Guidelines: Spell checkers with AI embedded in document drafting software. Experts should only use other AI spell checkers if they are local or offline tools. When using online tools, only short text segments should be processed. But no draft text from the assessment should be uploaded on AI tools. No IPBES or assessment content or identifiers should be included, in line with the principle of confidentiality. All corrections must be manually verified.

Grammar checkers:

Usage: During drafting and final editing.

Risks: Potential distortion of meaning; disclosure of text to external servers.

Guidelines: Experts may use AI grammar tools with the same caution as spell checkers. Suggestions must always be manually reviewed to ensure accuracy and preserve the intended meaning and tone.

Writing support:

Usage: Throughout drafting or when finalising text.

Risks: Confidentiality concerns; unintentional plagiarism; factual inaccuracies; homogenisation of style; distortion of intended meaning.

Guidelines: Experts may use AI tools for writing support, preferably in private local environments. When online tools are used, temporary or private modes may reduce data retention but do not replace confidentiality safeguards. AI suggestions must not be used as final assessment text without full rewriting and expert verification. Any text suggestions must be checked for factual accuracy, neutrality and originality. Representative prompts must be recorded in the DMR, along with their purpose, such as summarising, paraphrasing or harmonising tone. Prompts should be phrased neutrally to avoid introducing unintended interpretations or bias.

Coding usage

AI-powered coding and scripting assistants can support writing, debugging and optimising code used for data processing, figure generation or text analysis. These tools can improve efficiency but require careful validation. Experts must maintain full understanding of any code used in the assessment.

Coding and scripting support:

Usage: Supporting the writing and improving of code for data analysis, figure generation and text extraction.

Risks: Inaccurate or insecure code; accidental disclosure of confidential data, access tokens or API keys; reliance on opaque model logic; limited reproducibility.

Guidelines: Experts may use AI tools for code generation or debugging with caution. Confidential data, credentials and access tokens must never be shared with AI systems. All AI-generated code must be reviewed, tested and fully understood by the expert before use, including the logic and statistical assumptions embedded in the code. Exceptions for local or institutionally hosted tools may apply where confidentiality is ensured.

The use of AI-assisted coding must be documented in the DMR. Experts should also record representative prompts or instructions used for code generation or debugging, including their purpose, to support transparency and reproducibility. AI-generated code should not independently determine or select statistical models; methodological decisions must remain expert led.

Translational usage

AI translation tools can support inclusivity by facilitating multilingual participation and access to non-English materials. Their use must respect confidentiality, accuracy and traceability. AI translations of draft content must be used with caution and may only be processed through private or institutional systems that ensure confidentiality. Text processed through AI translation tools must be independently reviewed by experts fluent in the target language.

Translation of draft sections into English

Usage: Internal use for translation of draft materials.

Risks: Disclosure of confidential text; inaccurate or inconsistent translation; loss of nuance; dependency on unverifiable algorithms.

Guidelines: Experts may use private or institutional AI translation tools, preferably offline. Draft text should never be uploaded to public or third-party AI systems. Translations of primary sources of evidence should be processed in short sections. AI-translated sections should be clearly marked for internal review. All translations must be reviewed by experts fluent in English to ensure accuracy, consistency and adherence to assessment meaning. Representative prompts or translation settings, such as “translate to English for technical style”, should be noted in the DMR. Experts are responsible for synthesizing content for the assessment coming from the translated source materials (e.g. reports, papers or grey literature).

Translation of evidence materials

Usage: Internal use for translating source materials such as national reports or grey literature.

Risks: Misinterpretation; loss of contextual meaning; stylistic drift; potential over-reliance on automated outputs.

Guidelines: Experts may use AI tools to translate evidence materials, but translated outputs must always be reviewed by a domain expert fluent in the original language. Translations

should be used as an aid and not as a substitute for expert understanding. Any use of AI translation for evidence extraction should be documented in the DMR.

Translation of search terms

Usage: During the definition of literature search protocols.

Risks: Incorrect or misleading translations that alter search sensitivity or scope.

Guidelines: Experts may use AI tools to translate search terms, but all translations must be reviewed by a domain expert to ensure semantic accuracy and avoid misalignment in search strategies. Where AI is used, representative prompts and the resulting translated terms should be recorded in the DMR for transparency.

Literature search

AI can assist in expanding the scope of literature searches through the generation of search terms, identification of potentially relevant studies and summarisation of findings. However, AI tools must never replace systematic expert-led search methods. All AI-suggested references must be verified by experts for existence, accuracy and relevance.

Generation of search terms

Usage: Defining search protocols.

Risks: Overly broad or irrelevant results; missing key terms; model bias.

Guidelines: Experts may use AI tools to draft or expand search strings, provided results are refined and validated manually by domain experts. Representative prompts used to generate search terms should be documented in the DMR.

Search via general chatbots

Usage: Supplementing expert-based searches.

Risks: Fabricated citations; unverifiable sources; biased or incomplete reference lists; non transparent selection of references.

Guidelines: Experts must not rely on chatbots as primary search methods. They may use them only to explore topics or identify keywords, and all results must be independently checked. Any prompts used for exploratory searches must be documented in the DMR, including the intended scope of the query and representative wording, to support reproducibility and avoid misinterpretation.

Use of AI-based search tools

Usage: Initial screening of literature.

Risks: Incomplete database coverage; algorithmic bias; fabricated or irrelevant references; limited transparency regarding data sources.

Guidelines: Experts may combine AI-assisted search tools with established bibliographic databases such as OpenAlex, Scopus or Web of Science. All references identified through AI tools must be manually verified for existence and suitability. Limitations of AI search tools, including database coverage, filters and potential bias, should be documented in the DMR.

Literature and data analysis

AI can support large scale text or data analysis, but outputs must be critically validated. AI tools may assist in identifying patterns, summarising content or organising information, but they must not generate new scientific findings or independent interpretations.

PDF/Text analysis and synthesis

Usage: Extracting metadata, summarising results and categorising content.

Risks: Bias in model outputs; limited reproducibility; misclassification; fabricated; patterns; variation across model versions.

Guidelines: Experts may use AI tools to support text and PDF analysis, but all outputs must be cross checked using independent expert review or manual methods. AI model configurations and constraints should be recorded in the DMR. Prompts or instructions used to guide AI models in extracting, summarising or categorising text must be retained in the DMR together with representative outputs, supporting traceability of analytical steps. Where available, experts may refer to model cards or system cards describing the characteristics and limitations of the AI tools used.

Statistical analysis

Usage: Supporting hypothesis formulation or generating analysis code.

Risks: Inappropriate or non-transparent statistical methods; incorrect assumptions; model misspecification; fabricated outputs.

Guidelines: Experts must not use AI tools to autonomously perform statistical analyses, generate new results or interpret model outputs. AI may assist with drafting or improving code, but selection of methods, models and parameters must remain expert led. Any AI generated code must be reviewed, tested and fully understood before use. All decisions related to modelling and statistical interpretation must be made by experts based on established scientific practice. The use of AI and representative prompts must be documented in the DMR.

Figures

AI tools can help conceptualise or prototype figures but must never substitute expert verification, manual refinement or expert led data interpretation. All final figures included in IPBES assessments must be created and verified by experts to ensure accuracy, neutrality and reproducibility.

Conceptual figures

Usage: Drafting preliminary layouts or illustrations.

Risks: Copyright issues; biased or culturally insensitive imagery; inaccurate representations; lack of transparency in image generation.

Guidelines: Experts may use AI tools for early sketches or mock ups, but all final conceptual figures must be manually prepared and reviewed by experts. AI prompts used to generate or prototype figures, such as textual descriptions, layout suggestions or stylistic indications, should be included in the DMR. Experts should ensure that prompts do not contain copyrighted or culturally sensitive content and should verify that outputs do not introduce stereotypes or unintended interpretations.

Data figures

Usage: Generating or styling data visualisations.

Risks: Misleading scales; inappropriate styling; incorrect statistical assumptions; reduced reproducibility; opacity of data transformations.

Guidelines: Experts may use AI to prototype code for generating figures, but all final figures must be based on source data, rendered manually and fully validated by experts. AI generated visualisations should not be used directly in assessment drafts. Any use of AI to support data visualisation should be documented in the DMR, including representative

prompts used to request coding assistance. Experts must ensure that final figures accurately reflect underlying data and adhere to IPBES standards for transparency and reproducibility.

Review of assessment drafts

AI must not be used for reviewing IPBES drafts, as this would risk breaching confidentiality, undermining the credibility of the review process and compromising trust in the Platform. Draft report text must not be uploaded to any public or third-party AI system under any circumstances.

AI support in internal and external reviews

Usage: Strongly discouraged and generally not permitted.

Risks: Breach of confidentiality; disclosure of text outside authorised channels; biased or inaccurate feedback; erosion of trust in the review process; confusion between expert judgment and AI generated comments.

Guidelines: IPBES experts and reviewers must not upload draft text, review comments or any confidential material to AI systems. All reviews must be conducted independently and confidentially by designated experts. AI tools must not be used to generate, structure or edit review comments. Where experts rely on local or institutionally hosted tools for basic editorial support, no draft text may be shared beyond secured environments, and expert judgment must remain fully independent. Review comments generated or influenced by AI systems must not be submitted.

Implementation, monitoring and reporting

The Code of Practice on the use of artificial intelligence applies to all new and ongoing IPBES assessments and other knowledge synthesis processes. The expert groups preparing IPBES deliverables are required to adhere to its provisions. Each assessment TSU is responsible for supporting experts to ensure that the use of AI within its assessment follows this Code and that all relevant details are documented in the corresponding data and knowledge management reports (DMRs).

Compliance with this Code will be monitored through the review of DMRs and related documentation by the TSU on data and knowledge management. The TSU will report to the task force on the degree of compliance and on any recurring issues, challenges or good practices identified. Verification may include checking whether AI-generated content has been incorporated without disclosure, including through the examination of text consistency or the use of available reverse engineering tools, without relying on any single detection method. The task force will provide technical guidance to assessment TSUs and experts and will support measures that promote the responsible and ethical use of AI in all IPBES activities. During external review processes, any use of AI must be explicitly documented, including representative prompts, model names and relevant configuration details.

The task force on data and knowledge management will include in its regular reports to the Bureau and the Multidisciplinary Expert Panel information on the implementation of this Code, including lessons learned and proposals for refinement. The Code of Practice is a living document and will be reviewed regularly, at least every two years, to reflect new developments in AI technologies, ethical standards and relevant United Nations system principles and guidelines. Revisions will be proposed by the task force and submitted to the Bureau and the Multidisciplinary Expert Panel for endorsement.

Any emerging or unexpected issues concerning the use of artificial intelligence that are not covered in this Code will be brought to the attention of the IPBES secretariat and the technical support unit

on data and knowledge management, who will seek the guidance of the task force on data and knowledge management. Guidance provided through this process will be considered in future update processes of the Code.

The task force and the TSU on data and knowledge management, in cooperation with the secretariat and other task forces as relevant, will facilitate the development of training materials, guidance notes and awareness raising activities to support experts and TSUs in the ethical and responsible use of AI. These activities will encourage the sharing of experiences and good practices among assessments, strengthen a common understanding of AI use across IPBES and help ensure consistency in the application of this Code.

Glossary

This glossary complements existing definitions contained in IPBES documents, including the data and knowledge management policy, assessment glossaries and other relevant Platform decisions, such as the approach to recognising and working with Indigenous and local knowledge adopted in annex II to decision IPBES 5/1. Only additional or specific terms relevant to the Code of Practice on the use of artificial intelligence are defined below.

AI assisted workflow. Any step within the assessment process, such as literature search, data analysis, figure design or text editing, where AI tools are used. Each instance, including representative prompts and resulting outputs, should be transparently recorded in the relevant DMR.

Artificial intelligence. A collective term for computer based systems capable of performing tasks that normally require human intelligence, such as language processing, reasoning, pattern recognition or decision making. In the context of this Code, artificial intelligence refers specifically to systems that generate content, such as text, code or images, in response to user input. This includes large language models, image generation models and comparable tools.

Confidential content. Any unpublished draft material, personal data, review comments or internal discussion relating to IPBES assessments that must not be shared with external or online AI systems.

Generative AI. A type of artificial intelligence model that creates new outputs such as text, images, code or audio based on patterns learned from large volumes of data. Examples include large language models and image generation systems.

Generative output. The text, code, image or other content produced by a generative AI model in response to a prompt. Experts remain fully responsible for reviewing and validating such outputs.

Institutionally hosted AI systems. AI applications or models installed and executed on institutional infrastructure that is accessible only to members of the institution. These systems are preferred when working with confidential IPBES materials to ensure data security and compliance with confidentiality requirements.

Large language model. A type of AI model trained on extensive text corpora to generate and interpret natural language. Large language models can assist with summarisation, translation, coding and content generation, but their outputs are probabilistic and may contain factual or logical errors.

Locally hosted AI systems. AI applications or models executed on private or institutional infrastructure and accessible only to authorised users, often a single expert conducting an AI assisted analysis.

Model specification. A description of the AI system used, including the model name, version, provider and configuration parameters such as temperature or context length, and whether it was accessed online or locally. Such information should accompany AI related entries in DMRs to support transparency and reproducibility. For public chatbots and comparable systems, only the system name and model information may be available.

Online or third party AI systems. Commercial or public AI platforms accessed through the internet that process data externally. Their use in IPBES assessments requires explicit caution and disclosure and must not involve confidential content.

Prompt. A written instruction or query provided by the user to an AI system to generate a specific output. Representative prompts must be recorded in the DMR when AI tools are used for any step of the assessment process.